

Studies in Chain Transfer. Part VIII. Ethyl Methacrylate

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Chain-transfer coefficient, $C_s = (k_s/k_p)$, of 23 solvents has been determined in the polymerisation of ethyl methacrylate at 80°, using azo-bis-isobutyronitrile as a catalyst and compared with the C_s values of the respective solvents in methyl methacrylate polymerisation. The results obtained are in agreement with the view that free radical preferentially attacks the α -hydrogen. There is, however, no marked difference in the chain-transfer characteristics in ethyl methacrylate from that in methyl methacrylate, the relative trend being more or less same in both the cases.

In a previous communication¹, we have reported the results of the kinetic study with the higher esters of methacrylic acid. The present communication reports the results of chain-transfer study in the polymerisation of ethyl methacrylate, catalysed by azo-bis-isobutyronitrile.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details including purification of monomer, solvents, etc. were essentially the same as described earlier¹. The monomer ethyl methacrylate [I. C. I. (India) Ltd.] was purified by twice distilling under low pressure before use. The polymer was isolated by precipitation with ethanol-water mixture (70:30), followed by reprecipitation from acetone solution. Degree of polymerisation was calculated by using the equation¹:

$$[\eta] = 3.46 \times 10^3 [M]^{0.81}$$

Calculation of the Chain-transfer Coefficients in Catalysed Polymerisation

The fundamental equation² for chain-transfer study can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\bar{P}} = \sum C_x \frac{[X]}{[M]} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where X is any molecular species present in the system which can react with a growing free radical and C_x is the ratio of the rate constant of the transfer reaction to the rate of propagation, i.e.,

$$C_x = k_x/k_p$$

and is called the transfer coefficient with respect to X. In presence of a monomer M, a solvent S and a catalyst (initiator) I, in the system, the above expression becomes

$$1/\bar{P} = C_M + C_S \frac{[S]}{[M]} + C_I \frac{[I]}{[M]} + \frac{\delta^2}{[M]^2} R_p \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

1. Khanna *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, 58, 1827.

2. Palit and Das, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1954, A226, 82.

where $[M]$, $[S]$, $[I]$ stand for monomer, solvent, and catalyst concentration respectively; C_M , C_S , and C_I are the monomer, solvent, and catalyst (initiator) transfer coefficients, R_p , the overall rate of polymerisation, and δ stands for $k_t^{1/2}/k_p$. It is easily seen that if we have a catalyst and a solvent, where the rate is given by the usual equation of the type:

$$R_p = \frac{k_i}{\delta} [I]^{1/2} [M]^{2/3} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

we easily obtain

$$1/\bar{P} = C_M + C_S \frac{[S]}{[M]} + C_I \frac{[I]}{[M]} + \sqrt{k_i} \cdot \delta \frac{[I]^{1/2}}{[M]^{1/3}} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

which at constant $[I]/[M]$ and if k_i remains constant, becomes

$$1/\bar{P} = k (\text{constant}) + C_S \frac{[S]}{[M]} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

In such a case, we can follow a method similar to that of Mayo³ for uncatalysed polymerisation, viz., determination of slope of $1/\bar{P}$ against $[S]/[M]$ plot at constant $[I]/[M]$. The essential condition of validity of this equation is that experiments must be conducted over a range of $[S]/[M]$ such that $R_p/[M]^2$ remains constant at constant $[I]/[M]$. In such a case we shall get correct values of C_S , but k is not necessarily the same for all the solvents and neither it is equal to $1/P_0$, where P_0 is the degree of polymerisation for bulk polymerisation under otherwise identical conditions.

TABLE I

Chain-transfer constants for ethyl methacrylate polymerisation in various solvents at 80°.
Azo-bis-isobutyronitrile = 6.10×10^{-3} moles per litre of monomer.

Solvents.	$[S]/[M]$.	$[I]$.	$10^3/\bar{P}$.	$10^3 C_S$.
Benzene	1.42	1.150	29.00	0.81
	2.83	1.125	30.71	
	4.25	1.050	33.45	
	8.49	1.000	35.52	
Toluene	1.18	0.585	68.87	4.36
	2.71	0.515	80.58	
	8.20	0.355	101.37	
Ethylbenzene	1.03	0.545	75.19	14.28
	2.39	0.410	106.78	
	4.11	0.370	121.22	
Isopropylbenzene	0.90	0.515	80.58	20.87
	2.10	0.415	105.25	
	3.61	0.330	139.64	
	6.31	0.255	192.01	
n-Heptane	0.85	0.550	74.29	8.65
	1.99	0.460	92.68	
	3.42	0.430	100.69	
	6.98	0.370	121.22	

TABLE I (contd.)

Solvents.	$[\eta]/[M]$.	$[\eta]$.	$10^5/\bar{P}$.	10^5C_g .
	1.10	0.645	61.01	
	1.93	0.615	64.72	
Cyclohexane	2.33	0.552	73.06	9.28
	4.66	0.460	92.68	
<i>n</i> -Butanol	1.37	0.706	54.61	
	2.74	0.650	60.46	
	4.12	0.637	61.99	4.54
	6.87	0.518	80.06	
<i>sec.</i> -Butanol	1.41	0.760	49.87	
	2.82	0.580	69.64	16.04
	4.23	0.450	95.15	
Isobutanol	1.35	0.812	45.92	
	2.71	0.725	52.85	4.45
	6.77	0.575	70.32	
<i>t</i> -Butanol	1.34	0.750	50.68	
	2.67	0.650	60.46	
	4.01	0.630	62.61	4.17
	6.69	0.550	72.29	
Ethanol	2.15	0.640	61.61	
	4.31	0.590	68.12	4.29
	10.77	0.440	97.84	
Acetone	3.99	0.375	119.23	1.02
	6.85	0.365	123.27	
	11.99	0.355	127.61	
Methyl ethyl ketone	3.18	0.385	115.42	
	5.62	0.370	121.23	2.52
	9.83	0.345	131.89	
Methyl <i>n</i> -amyl ketone	0.92	0.560	69.64	
	2.15	0.525	78.68	7.02
	3.68	0.475	89.05	
	5.53	0.425	102.16	
Acetophenone	1.07	0.800	40.79	
	2.15	0.780	48.28	2.81
	3.22	0.720	52.85	
Acetonyl acetone	1.23	0.795	47.17	
	3.68	0.675	57.70	2.36
	7.36	0.635	62.23	
Acetic acid	2.19	0.710	54.23	
	5.13	0.680	57.21	0.95
	8.79	0.660	59.35	
	13.19	0.610	65.02	
Ethyl acetate	1.28	0.490	85.09	
	3.00	0.430	100.69	9.19
	5.15	0.370	121.23	

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TABLE I (contd.)

Solvents.	[S]/[M].	[η].	$10^3/P$.	$10^5 C_s$.
Chloroform	1.58	0.558	72.94	7.03
	3.68	0.466	91.24	
	9.47	0.351	129.38	
Methylchloroform	1.70	0.578	70.22	5.36
	*4.00	0.498	83.96	
	6.85	0.433	99.80	
CCl ₄	1.30	0.600	66.75	9.01
	3.04	0.500	83.54	
	5.22	0.425	102.16	
Tetrachloroethane	1.19	0.775	48.66	3.11
	2.18	0.712	54.05	
	3.57	0.635	62.23	
	7.14	0.525	78.68	
Chlorobenzene	1.24	0.630	62.61	4.36
	4.95	0.520	79.43	
	8.66	0.450	95.15	

TABLE II

Comparison of chain-transfer values (C_s) of diff. solvents in the polymerisation of styrene, methyl acrylate, methyl and ethyl methacrylates at 80°.

Solvent.	Styrene.	Me-acrylate ¹² .	Me-methacrylate ¹⁰ .	Et-methacrylate.
Benzene	*0.59 × 10 ⁻³	3.26 × 10 ⁻³	0.50 × 10 ⁻³	0.81 × 10 ⁶
Toluene	*3.14	17.75	3.20	4.36
Ethylbenzene	*11.09	60.56	11.67	14.28
Isopropylbenzene	*13.27	69.66	14.55	20.67
n-Heptane	*7.00	..	..	8.65
Cyclohexane	‡1.56	0.27	1.00	9.28
n-Butanol	4.00	27.47	2.50	4.54
Isobutanol	..	24.96	2.50	4.45
Sec.-Butanol	8.00	141.40	8.50	16.04
t-Butanol	3.45	3.89	1.00	4.17
Acetone	4.35	6.22	2.25	1.02
Methyl ethyl ketone	15.38	32.38	7.00	2.52
Acetic acid	2.09	..	..	0.95
Ethyl acetate	..	..	2.40	9.19
CCl ₄	1810.00	13.23	23.93	9.01
Chloroform	..	21.44	14.00	7.03
Methylchloroform	..	5.74	6.00	3.36
Tetrachloroethane	..	9.32	2.00	3.11
Chlorobenzene	..	9.86	2.00	4.26

*Calculated for 80° from the data of Gregg and Mayo⁹.

‡Nozaki, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 2, 328.

DISCUSSION

Of the existing data on chain transfer with solvents in catalysed polymerisation, the work of Basu *et al.*⁴ is of special interest. They have established that chain-transfer constant, calculated from the slope of $1/\bar{P}$ against $[S]/[M]$ at constant $[I]/[M]$, is not affected by the presence of low concentrations of catalyst, when the transfer with the catalyst is negligible. So, the kinetics of solvent transfer in presence of a catalyst becomes simplified. Breitenbach and Schindler⁵, Arlmen and Wagner⁶, and Baysal and Tobolsky⁷ have proved that azo-bis-isobutyronitrile is a better catalyst than benzoyl peroxide in the polymerisation of styrene and methyl methacrylate. This catalyst is known to decompose unimolecularly⁸, having the same decomposition rate, in a number of solvents. It has been observed in the bulk polymerisation of ethyl methacrylate¹ with azo-bis-isobutyronitrile as catalyst that R_p vs. $1/\bar{P}$ plot at varying concentrations of catalyst provides a fairly good straight line, indicating negligible transfer coefficient of the catalyst in the polymerisation of ethyl methacrylate.

Solvent Transfer.—Since it is assumed that the solvent molecules do not contribute in any way to the initiation reaction, their sole effect may be presumed to be due to their activity as chain-transferring agents. Relative efficiency of various solvents is reflected in their chain-transfer constants in Table I. In Table II, the C_s values of various solvents in the polymerisation of ethyl methacrylate at 80° are compared with the C_s values for the same solvents in methyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate, and styrene at the same temperature.

Hydrocarbon Solvents.—The chain-transfer constants for the hydrocarbon solvents in the polymerisation of ethyl methacrylate are slightly greater than their corresponding values obtained in uncatalysed thermal polymerisation of methyl methacrylate at the same temperature. The chain-transferring capacity of the hydrocarbons increases in the order: benzene < toluene < ethylbenzene < isopropylbenzene; this is also the case with styrene⁹, methyl methacrylate¹⁰⁻¹¹, methyl acrylate¹², vinyl acetate², and acrylonitrile¹³. The explanation based on the reactivity of benzylic hydrogen is valid in this case also. Cyclohexane, which is a poor transfer agent in methyl methacrylate and styrene polymerisation, shows high transfer activity with polyethyl methacrylate radical. C_s value of cyclohexane (9.28×10^{-5}) is closer to that of *n*-heptane (8.65×10^{-5}). This anomalous behaviour of cyclohexane in this case is difficult to account for. It must be admitted, however, that to form a definite conclusion one should really compare the activation energies of the transfer process rather than the transfer constants at a particular temperature.

Alcohols.—The concept of the reactive hydrogen undergoing transfer by free-radical attack is clearly demonstrated from the data of isomeric butanols. In ethyl methacrylate

4. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1952, **A214**, 247.

5. *Monatsh.*, 1952, **83**, 724.

6. *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1952, **9**, 581.

7. *Ibid.*, 1952, **8**, 529.

8. Lewis and Walling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 747.

9. Gregg and Mayo, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, **2**, 328.

10. Basu *et al.*, *Proc., Roy. Soc.*, 1950, **A202**, 495.

11. Chadha *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **53**, 240.

12. Sen *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, **40**, 729.

13. Das *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1955, **A227**, 252.

as also in case of other monomers studied, *sec.*-butanol with a tertiary hydrogen atom is easily attacked by the growing polymer radical. The chain-transfer coefficients of the butanols are about double in ethyl methacrylate than in methyl methacrylate. Ethanol, in which the polymer is soluble, has almost equal chain-transfer value as *n.*, *iso.*, and *t.*-butanol.

Ketones.—The chain-transfer constants of the ketonic solvents follow the same sequence as in the other monomers studied in this series and are in agreement with the α -hydrogen transfer. The C_s values of the ketones are lower in ethyl methacrylate than in methyl methacrylate.

Acid and Ester.—The chain-transfer constant of ethyl acetate (9.19×10^{-5}) is greater by an order than that of acetic acid (0.95×10^{-5}) in ethyl methacrylate polymerisation. Identical values for these two solvents were obtained in the thermal polymerisation of methyl methacrylate¹⁰. This wide difference in the value of the chain-transfer constant for the two structurally similar monomers is not clearly understood. The polymer is freely soluble in ethyl acetate and acetic acid and there is no phase separation during the course of polymerisation, although the yield of polymer is higher in acetic acid than in ethyl acetate. This may be due to the increase in the rate of initiation in acetic acid medium, which makes the application of equation (5) for calculation of C_s of doubtful validity.

Chlorinated Solvents.—The peculiar behaviour of chloro compounds towards free radical reaction has already been discussed¹² in detail. The activity of the chloro compounds in ethyl methacrylate follows the same order as in methyl methacrylate: $\text{CCl}_4 > \text{CHCl}_3 > \text{CH}_3\text{CCl}_3 > \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl} > \text{CHCl}_2\text{CHCl}_2$. The values of the transfer constants of CCl_4 and CHCl_3 are, however, greater in methyl methacrylate than in ethyl methacrylate. The order of reactivity of CCl_4 and CHCl_3 changes completely in the case of methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile where abstraction of the tertiary hydrogen from chloroform is preferred to a chlorine atom from CCl_4 . Substitution of the hydrogen atom of chloroform by a methyl group decreases the chain-transfer capacity of the solvent, as will be evident from the C_s value of methylechloroform (5.37×10^{-5}) and chloroform (7.03×10^{-5}). *sym.*-Tetrachloroethane having two tertiary hydrogen atoms has a lower transfer constant ($C_s = 3.11 \times 10^{-5}$) than chloroform. This difference in activity may be attributed to the difference in the number of halogen atoms linked to the carbon atom carrying transferable hydrogen. The behaviour is same as in the case of methacrylate and other monomers. The transfer constant of chlorobenzene is higher in ethyl methacrylate than in methyl methacrylate.

The higher transfer activity of CCl_4 , as compared to CHCl_3 , can be explained in terms of polar effect due to contribution to the transition state, as suggested by Walling¹⁴. The resonance stabilisation of the transition state depends on the electron-attracting or electron-donating nature of the polymer radical. The higher activity of CCl_4 in the polymerisation of styrene and vinyl acetate is due to the electron-donating nature of styryl and vinyl acetate radicals towards CCl_4 acting as an electron-acceptor. Similar arguments have been advanced by Fuhrman and Mesrobian¹⁵ in their chain-transfer study with CBr_4 in styrene polymerisation. This view has been further substantiated by the work of Bamford and White¹⁶, who used tertiary amines as transfer agent in the polymerisation of acrylonitrile.

14. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2561.

15. *Ibid.*, 1954, 76, 3281.

16. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 716.

The small difference in the reactivity of CCl_4 and CHCl_3 in the polymerisation of methyl methacrylate and ethyl methacrylate is consistent with the fact that the poly-radicals from these monomers act as electron-acceptor in the transition state.

The chain-transfer study in ethyl methacrylate does not reveal any marked difference in the transfer behaviour from that in methyl methacrylate. This may be due to the fact that steric hindrance due to slight increase in the ester group is not sufficient to affect the transfer step, as will also be evidenced from their $\delta (=k_t/k_p)$ values¹.

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